

NBS4 AQUAMISSION

WP1 Monitoring of pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminant D1.1 Report on screening results

CDP
2026

NBS4AQUAMMISSION: Nature-Based Systems Mission for Aquatic Biodiversity Enhancement: Reducing Pharmaceutical Products Pollution in Urban and Rural Environments

Funding Acknowledgment: This document is based upon work from NBS4AQUAMMISSION project, funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership under the 2023 – 2024 BiodivNBS joint call for research proposals, co-funded by the European Commission and with the following funding agencies: DK, Innovationsfonden DK (IFD); Ireland, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Italy, Ministry of Universities and Research (MUR); NO, The Research Council of Norway (RCN); SP, Agencia Española de Investigación (AEI); Türkiye, The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK).

Project acronym	NBS4AQUAMMISSION
Project title	Nature Based Systems Mission for Aquatic Biodiversity Enhancement: Reducing Pharmaceutical Products Pollution in Urban and Rural Environments
Responsible	Amir Gholipour and Pedro Carvalho, AU (Work Package 1 responsible)
Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable title	Report on screening results
Work package	WP1 Monitoring of pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants
Delivery date	24 June 2026
Availability	Public (10.5281/zenodo.20826534)
Communication contact	Pedro Carvalho (Pedro.carvalho@envs.au.dk)

Version	Date	Modification	Author(s)
0.0	20 December 2025	Draft version	Amir Gholipour (AU)
1.0	20 January 2026	Revised-Updated version	Amir Gholipour (AU)
1.1	4 April 2026	Revision	Pedro Carvalho (AU)
2.0	18 April 2026	Revised-Updated version	Amir Gholipour (AU)
2.1	27 April 2026	Revision	Pedro Carvalho (AU)
2.2	1 May 2026	Revision	Pedro Carvalho (AU)
2.3	18 May 2026	Revision	Amir Gholipour (AU)
3.0	23 June 2026	Revised-Updated version	Pedro Carvalho (AU)
3.1	24 June 2026	Revision	Amir Gholipour (AU)
3.2	24 June 2026	Final polishing	Pedro Carvalho (AU)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABBREVIATIONS.....	ii
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
INTRODUCTION.....	6
ABOUT NBS4AQUAMISSION.....	6
NBS4AQUAMISSION PARTNERS.....	6
Monitoring of pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants objectives.....	8
Pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants.....	8
Non-target and suspect screening.....	9
NBS4AQUAMISSION Demo Sites.....	10
MATERIALS AND METHODS.....	11
Sample Collection, Transport and Preservation.....	11
LC-HRMS workflow.....	12
Data analysis.....	12
RESULT AND DISCUSSION.....	13
CONCLUSION.....	15
ANNEX 1: NBS4AQUAMISSION suspect list.....	16

ABBREVIATIONS

AEI	Agencia Española de Investigación
ARB	Angiotensin II receptor blocker
AU	Aarhus University
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CCE	Collision energy
CENTA	Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, Junta de Andalucía
CNS	Central nervous system
CWP	Internal method/project reference
D1.1	Deliverable 1.1
DK	DK
EIC	Extracted ion chromatogram
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ES	SP
ESI	Electrospray ionization
EU	European Union
GC	Gas chromatography
GTU	Gebze Technical University
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
HRMS	High-resolution mass spectrometry
IDA	Information-dependent acquisition
IFD	Innovationsfonden DK
LC	Liquid chromatography
LC-HRMS	Liquid chromatography–high-resolution mass spectrometry
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry
M1	Milestone 1
M6	Milestone 6
M27	Milestone 27
MUR	Ministry of Universities and Research
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
NIBIO	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
NO	NO
NTS	Non-target screening
OMP	Organic micropollutant

OMPs	Organic micropollutants
PE	Population equivalent
PNEC	Predicted no-effect concentration
PP	Pharmaceutical products
PPs	Pharmaceutical products
QTOF	Quadrupole time-of-flight
RCN	The Research Council of NO
RP	Reversed phase
SCIEX	Sciex instrument platform / manufacturer name
SO1	Strategic Objective 1
SO3	Strategic Objective 3
T1.1	Task 1.1
T1.2	Task 1.2
T1.3	Task 1.3
T1.4	Task 1.4
TP	Transformation product
TPs	Transformation products
TÜBİTAK	The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye
UCD	University College Dublin
UJA	University of Jaén
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work package
WPs	Work packages

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable D1.1 reports the outcomes of Task 1.1 (M1–M6) within WP1 of NBS4AQUAMISSION, where Aarhus University (AU) conducted the first round of suspect and non-target screening to characterize pharmaceutical products (PP) and other organic micropollutants (OMPs) at three demo sites in Denmark (DK), Norway (NO), and Spain (SP). The demo site in Turkey will be analyzed once the samples are received at AU. This screening establishes the project's baseline chemical profiles for the inlet waters of the different nature-based solutions being studied under the project and supports objectives SO1 (pollution characterization) and SO3 (NbS performance monitoring).

Suspect screening was conducted on samples from the inlets and outlets of three of the four project demo sites. Using LC-HRMS, a broad suite of pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, transformation products, pesticides, and lifestyle markers was detected across all locations. Results showed the presence of several high-intensity, frequently occurring compounds, revealing both common cross-site markers and site-specific pollution signatures.

From the hundreds of features detected, a consistent group of **eight compounds** was identified across DK, NO, and SP. These include tilmicosin (veterinary macrolide antibiotic), tetroxoprim (antibacterial agent), dipyridamole (antiplatelet/vasodilator), protionamide (antitubercular agent), etofenprox (pyrethroid insecticide), chlorcyclizine (first-generation antihistamine), diclofenac (NSAID analgesic), and DEET (insect repellent). Among these, only diclofenac and DEET, are already present in the existing WP1 targeted LC-MS/MS list (~60 compounds).

Based on the prioritisation criteria (signal intensity, detection frequency, transnational occurrence, and under-studied status), two compounds - **tilmicosin** and **tetroxoprim** - are recommended as **Tier 1 priority additions** due to their high signal-to-noise ratios, 100 % library matches, and relevance for antimicrobial resistance surveillance. The other four compounds - **dipyridamole, protionamide, etofenprox, and chlorcyclizine** - are recommended as **Tier 2 additions** for inclusion in future targeted monitoring due to their consistent detection, distinct use patterns, and emerging concern for under-studied classes (e.g. antihistamines, pyrethroids) justify their inclusion for evaluating NbS performance. These compounds are recommended for addition in the targeted LC-MS/MS method (Task 1.2) for delivering an up to date monitoring of OMPs (Task 1.3).

Site-specific signatures were also observed: antibiotics and transformation products were prominent across all sites, with DK showing high signals for tilmicosin and chlorcyclizine, NO showing high dipyridamole levels in outlet samples, and SP showing both analgesics and multiple antibiotics. These OMP fingerprints define the baseline “chemical cocktails” needed to evaluate NbS removal efficiency under WP2 and to interpret ecotoxicological responses under WP3.

INTRODUCTION

ABOUT NBS4AQUAMISSION

The NBS4AQUAMISSION project directly addresses the profound footprint of anthropogenic activities, particularly pollution, as a key driver of biodiversity loss in aquatic ecosystems. The Living Planet Index reported an 83% decline in freshwater species from 1970 to 2012¹, largely due to pollution, including PP, from essential human activities. The project's mission is to leverage a combination of treatment wetlands, mimicking natural ecosystems.

The project is defined by its transdisciplinary approach, assembling expertise from the biological, environmental, chemical, economic, educational, and anthropological fields. The diverse team plays a crucial role in understanding the complex relationships between biodiversity, ecosystem services, and social systems. To test its efficacy, the solution will be validated at a pilot scale in four demonstration sites spanning a wide geographical range in Europe: NO, DK, SP, and Turkey.

NBS4AQUAMISSION PARTNERS

The project partners (Figure 1, Table 1), who come from six countries, are highly diverse, encompassing academic institutions, public administration, and a private company, further enhancing the project's multidisciplinary nature. The leader is the centre for Advanced Studies in Earth Sciences, Energy and Environment from the University of Jaén (SP).

Figure 1. Countries participating in the NBS4AQUAMISSION project.

¹ Williams- Subiza & Epele. 2021. Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems, 31(9), 2469-2480.

TABLE 1. NBS4AQUAMISSION partners

Center for Advanced Studies in Earth Sciences, Energy and Environment, University of Jaén (UJA)	SP
Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, Junta de Andalucía (CENTA)	SP
Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University (AU)	DK
Killian Water APS (KW)	DK
Environment and Natural Resources, Hydrology and Water Environment (NIBIO)	NO
School of Architecture, Planning and Environmental Policy, University College of Dublin (UCD)	Ireland
Department of Agriculture, University Mediterranea of Reggio Calabria (UNIRC)	Italy
Environmental Engineering Department, Gebze Technical University (GTU)	Turkey

Monitoring of pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants objectives

The primary activity of WP1 in NBS4AQUAMISSION is to establish robust analytical workflows that characterise pharmaceutical products (PP) and organic emerging contaminants across NBS4AQUAMISSION demo sites, and to translate screening data into actionable monitoring for NBS performance assessment. This is implemented through a centralised analytical hub at Aarhus University (AU), which coordinates sample analysis from all partners in support of NBS4AQUAMISSION SO1 (initial pollution characterisation) and SO3 (NBS effectiveness monitoring).

The general goals of WP1 are to: (i) improve knowledge of PP pollution profiles, spatial variability, and annual trends in European wastewaters; (ii) characterise site-specific emerging contaminants through suspect and non-target screening to inform updates of targeted methods; (iii) enable long-term monitoring of PP and transformation products (TPs) to evaluate NbS removal efficiency; (iv) identify priority compounds for risk assessment and regulatory relevance; and (v) generate harmonised datasets to support NbS optimisation and biodiversity protection strategies.

To achieve these goals, WP1 pursues four key operational objectives: (i) comprehensive suspect screening (T1.1) across the project demo sites to map PP “cocktails”; (ii) method evolution through iterative updating of target LC-MS/MS methods (T1.2) based on screening hits from T1.1 for routine quantification in T1.3; (iii) PP transformation products tracking using HRMS workflows (T1.4) to link parent compound removal to downstream risks; and (iv) data centralisation through delivery of treated datasets (D1.3) to UJA, KW, GTU, and NIBIO for integrated NbS evaluation and project-wide water quality management.

This approach directly addresses current knowledge gaps in PP variability and NbS performance and provides foundational data for D1.1 (Screening report, M6) and Milestone M1 (“Improve knowledge on PP and other emerging contaminants in European wastewaters, as well as their annual variability,” M27).

Pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants

Pharmaceutical products and organic emerging contaminants, also referred to as organic micropollutants or trace organic contaminants,

comprise a broad spectrum of natural and anthropogenic substances, including PP their metabolites and transformation products (TPs), industrial chemicals, biocides, and household products that are now ubiquitous in wastewaters and aquatic ecosystems worldwide. Within the European Water Framework Directive, many of these organic pollutants are classified as priority hazardous substances or contaminants of emerging concern, and the most recent revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive explicitly includes PP and organic emerging contaminants with specific treatment targets, reflecting their growing regulatory relevance. Each year, hundreds of new chemicals are introduced into the environment, underscoring the need for advanced analytical approaches to characterise exposure and support risk-based management strategies.

NBS4AQUAMMISSION addresses these challenges in WP1 through a two-tiered analytical strategy: i) suspect and non-target screening (T1.1) using LC-HRMS to characterise PP and other compounds at the demo sites, and ii) subsequent updates of targeted LC-MS/MS methods (T1.2) for routine quantification (T1.3), including TPs (T1.4). This centralised workflow at AU supports SO1 (baseline profiling) and SO3 (NbS performance), providing results for method refinement and datasets for risk assessment. The overarching aim is to enable dynamic refinement of target methods to track NbS efficacy against complex organic micropollutant mixtures and thereby enhance aquatic biodiversity protection.

Non-target and suspect screening

Recent advances in analytical instrumentation have enabled comprehensive non-target screening approaches, allowing detection and tentative identification of substances in environmental samples without prior specification of target analytes, and thus supporting unbiased exploration of the chemical space. High-resolution mass spectrometers (HRMS) with high mass accuracy, enable the simultaneous detection of several features. Commonly used HRMS platforms for NTS in wastewater include Quadrupole Time-of-Flight (QTOF) and Orbitrap systems coupled

to liquid chromatography (LC) for polar compounds or gas chromatography (GC) for semi-volatiles^{2,3,4}.

Within WP1, screening activities in NBS4AQUAMISSION focused on suspect screening rather than full non-target screening, using a predefined list of pharmaceutical products and other organic micropollutants. Suspect screening targets “known unknowns,” where exact masses and, where available, fragment spectra are predicted from databases or internal method libraries, enabling efficient interrogation of complex wastewater matrices against an evidence-based suspect list.

In this deliverable (D1.1), suspect screening results from samples from three of the four NBS4AQUAMISSION demo sites are reported.

NBS4AQUAMISSION Demo Sites

NbS for PP removal constitutes the core technological focus of NBS4AQUAMISSION, providing innovative green infrastructure to mitigate wastewater-derived pollution and protect aquatic biodiversity across urban-rural gradients. Within the project, four pilot-scale treatment wetlands operating across a north-south European transect (NO, DK, SP, Turkey), are used to assess PP and organic micropollutant removal, associated ecotoxicological risk reduction, and potential biodiversity benefits under contrasting climatic and hydrological conditions.

² Hayward, D.G., Wong, J.W., Zhang, K., Chang, J., Shi, F., Banerjee, K., Yang, P., 2011. Multiresidue pesticide analysis in ginseng and spinach by nontargeted and targeted screening procedures. *J. AOAC Int.* 94, 1741–1751. <https://doi.org/10.5740/jaoacint.SGEHayward>

³ Rostkowski, P., Haglund, P., Aalizadeh, R., Alygizakis, N., Thomaidis, N., Arandes, J.B., Nizzetto, P.B., Booij, P., Budzinski, H., Brunswick, P., Covaci, A., Gallampois, C., Grosse, S., Hindle, R., Ipolyi, I., Jobst, K., Kaserzon, S.L., Leonards, P., Lestremau, F., Letzel, T., Magnér, J., Matsukami, H., Moschet, C., Oswald, P., Plassmann, M., Slobodnik, J., Yang, C., 2019. The strength in numbers: comprehensive characterization of house dust using complementary mass spectrometric techniques. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-019-01615-6>

⁴ Thurman, E.M., Ferrer, I., Fernández-Alba, A.R., 2005. Matching unknown empirical formulas to chemical structure using LC/MS TOF accurate mass and database searching: Example of unknown pesticides on tomato skins. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1067, 127–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2004.11.007>

Table 1 provides an overview of the four sites, including country, influent water type, NbS configuration, scale, and WP1 sampling strategy used for the D1.1 baseline. Detailed engineering designs, operational settings, and broader monitoring protocols for these pilots are to be reported in other project deliverables and are therefore only summarised here to provide context for the suspect-screening results.

TABLE 2. Overview of NBS4AQUAMISSION Demo Sites and WP1 Sampling for D1.1

Pilot	Country	Water Type	Technology	Surface Area	Population Equivalent	Flow Rate	WP1 Sampling	# Samples
1	NO	Urban stream (contaminated with wastewater)	Surface flow wetland (5 interconnected ponds, Renseparken WPP)	~6500 m ²	21,500 PE	Variable	Inlet/Outlet	3
2	DK	Domestic wastewater	Rhizosph'air (no septic pre-treatment, sludge/water co-treatment, groundwater recharge)	Site-specific	Rural eco-village	Variable	Inlet	2
3	SP	Small town wastewater	Vertical subsurface flow wetland (6 units)	150 m ²	2,000 PE	6-7 m ³ /day	Inlet	1
4	Turkey	Pre-treated WWTP effluent	Vertical subsurface flow (3 ponds, substrate mods for Rhizosph'air)	75 m ²	To be determined	4-5 m ³ /day	Inlet/Outlet	To be determined

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection, Transport and Preservation

DK (Rhizosph'air eco-village) samples comprised two 24h composite inlets: one in Aug 2025, and the other one in Sep 2025 both collected via autosampler - capturing intra-seasonal variability in domestic wastewater pre-NbS. NO (Renseparken WPP) provided three grab samples: two inlets and one outlet collected in Aug 2025. SP, (CENTA research facility in

Carrión de los Céspedes) contributed one grab inlet sample collected in Sep 2025. Due to delays on the Turkish side, followed by logistical problems with sample shipping, no Turkey samples were received and therefore included for this screening round. System details were summarised in Table 1 above.

All followed WP1 protocols outlined in “Sampling guidelines for micropollutants analysis” issued by Aarhus University (AU), emphasising glass containers, minimal handling, immediate cooling (~5°C), and freezing at -20°C until shipment. Transport occurred via express courier in thermal boxes with dry ice/ice gel packs; samples arrived at AU within 24h days at <5°C and were immediately frozen at -20°C. LC-HRMS analysis commenced at the latest within 1 month of sample receipt.

LC-HRMS workflow

Samples were analysed as one single batch. Only reversed-phase positive ionisation data - aligned with NBS4AQUAMISSION target LC-MS/MS workflows (T1.3) - were processed for this D1.1 report.

Frozen (-20 °C) wastewater samples were thawed, vortexed, and centrifuged (4000 g, 7 min, 4 °C) to remove particulates. 900 µL supernatants transferred to HPLC autosampler vials, spiked with 100 µL internal standard mix (300 µg/L total), and analysed in duplicate by direct injection (10 µL) onto a LC-QTOF-MS 6600 system (SCIEX, USA). Separation was achieved on Acquity UPLC BEH Shield RP18 (1.7 µm, 2.1×100 mm) at 30 °C; mobile phases A: 0.1% formic acid in water, B: 0.1% formic acid in methanol. Gradient: 0 min 0% B, 0-9 min 80% B, 9-11 min 100% B, 11-16 min 100% B, 16-16.1 min 0% B, 16.1-18 min 0% B (flow 0.4 mL/min). ESI+ source: 500 °C gas temp, 5300 V capillary, GS1/GS2 50/50 psi, CUR 30 psi. Information-Dependent Acquisition (IDA): TOF MS (100-1000 Da, 0.25 s accum.), followed by 10 MS/MS (top >100 cps peaks, 25-1000 Da, 0.04 s/ion, CE 30±15 eV).

Data analysis

Data was processed in SCIEX OS (version:1.6.1.29803) using a processing method configured for targeted identification of compounds using SCIEX HR-MS/MS libraries (Metabolites 1.0, Antibiotics 1.0, Forensics 2.1) covering a total of 2439 compounds of interest for the NBS4AQUAMISSION project. The processing method was based on the Sciex algorithm MQ4 that uses a peak modelling approach using a representative sample - in this case, we used one of our real wastewater

influent samples - to establish baseline integration parameters. The algorithm then applies these parameters consistently across all samples in the batch, reducing variability between analysts and improving reproducibility. In brief, minimum peak width of 6 points, minimum peak height of 100, XIC with a width of 0.02 Da, precursor mass tolerance of 0.04 Da. Flagging rules were set to equal weight acceptable differences for mass error (< 5 ppm), fragment mass error (< 5 ppm), error in retention time (<2.5 %), % difference in isotope ratio (< 5%), and library hit score (>70). A library hit score ensures matching of MS² experimental data, with Sciex HR-MS/MS libraries – providing a level 2 confidence identification level⁵, as per the commonly used standard notification in the research community. Thus, results further reported only include data for the two top confidence levels, level 1 (confirmation by reference standard, when available at AU) and level 2 (probable structure by library match). Table 3 presents the Schymanski Levels for suspect and non-target screening identification confidence.

Table 3. Explanation of the Schymanski levels

Level	Confidence	Evidence required
Level 1	Confirmed structure	Reference standard (retention time + MS/MS match)
Level 2	Probable structure	Library MS/MS match (no standard)
Level 3	Tentative candidate	Diagnostic MS/MS evidence or literature
Level 4	Unequivocal formula	Molecular formula only
Level 5	Exact mass	m/z only

The results from the MQ4 workflow were further manually quality assured:

- i) A compound is only reported if it can be identified through double injections and is not present in the procedural blanks.
- ii) The quality of the MS² spectra match was cross validated, with at least three diagnostic ions matching.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Screening of the LC-HRMS/MS data against the comprehensive spectral libraries identified a wide range of organic micropollutants across the three NBS4AQUAMISSION demo sites (DK, NO, SP). The results are appended to this report in the form of an Excel database. From the

⁵ Shimadzinky paper – confidence level Emma L. Schymanski, Junho Jeon, Rebekka Gulde, Kathrin Fenner, Matthias Ruff, Heinz P. Singer, and Juliane Hollender. *Environmental Science & Technology* 2014 48 (4), 2097-2098 DOI: 10.1021/es5002105

hundreds of features detected with a signal-to-noise ratio above 4 and a library match score $\geq 75\%$, a subset of ten compounds was selected based on detection frequency, signal intensity, chemical class diversity, and relevance to under-studied or emerging contaminant groups. These compounds, summarised in Table 4, include veterinary and human antibiotics (tilmicosin, tetroxoprim, protionamide), cardiovascular pharmaceuticals (dipyridamole), insecticides (etofenprox, DEET), antihistamines (chlorcyclizine), and analgesics (diclofenac). Their occurrence across multiple sites and high signal intensities (e.g., tilmicosin $S/N > 187,000$; chlorcyclizine $S/N > 11,000$) confirm that non-targeted screening successfully captures environmentally relevant compounds that may escape routine targeted monitoring.

TABLE 4. Selected detected compounds by LC-HRMS ($S/N > 4$; aggregated by compound)

Name	CAS Nr.	Occurrence (n/10)	Group	Category
Tilmicosin	108050 54 0	4	Antibiotics	Macrolide antibiotic
Tetroxoprim	53808 87 0	6	Antibiotics	Antibacterial agent
Dipyridamole	58 32 2	6	Pharmaceuticals	Antiplatelet/vasodilator
Protionamide	14222 60 7	4	Antibiotics	Antitubercular agent
Etofenprox	80844 07 1	4	Other OMP	Pyrethroid insecticide
Chlorcyclizine	82 93 9	3	Pharmaceuticals	Antihistamine (first-generation)
Diclofenac	15307 86 5	5	Pharmaceuticals	NSAID analgesic
DEET	134 62 3	7	Other OMP	Insect repellent

Comparison with the existing WP1 targeted LC-MS/MS list (~60 compounds) revealed that only three of these eight high-frequency, cross-site compounds, diclofenac, and DEET are currently covered by the in-house method. The remaining compounds (tilmicosin, tetroxoprim, dipyridamole, protionamide, etofenprox, and chlorcyclizine) were absent from the targeted list, representing a gap in analytical coverage (Table 5).

TABLE 5. Target vs. suspect screening comparison

Suspect Screening High Frequency Compound	Found in All Sites?	Present in AU Target List?	Recommendation
Tilmicosin	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 1)
Tetroxoprim	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 1)
Dipyridamole	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 2)
Protionamide	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 2)
Etofenprox	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 2)
Chlorcyclizine	✓ Yes	✗ No	Add (Tier 2)
Diclofenac	✓ Yes	✓ Yes	Already targeted

DEET	✓ Yes	✓ Yes	Already targeted
------	-------	-------	------------------

Based on these findings, we recommend updating the WP1 targeted LC-MS/MS method (Task T1.2) to include the six missing compounds. Tilmicosin and tetroxoprim are proposed as **Tier 1 additions** due to their very high signal intensities, transnational occurrence, and relevance as veterinary and human antibiotic markers for antimicrobial resistance surveillance. Dipyridamole, protionamide, etofenprox, and chlorcyclizine are proposed as **Tier 2 additions**; while somewhat more context-dependent, their consistent detection, distinct use patterns, and emerging concern for under-studied classes (e.g., antihistamines, pyrethroids) justify their inclusion for evaluating PP pollution patterns, NbS treatment performance (WP2), and removal efficiency/risk reduction (WP3). This expansion of the target list will align suspect screening outputs with routine monitoring capabilities and strengthen the project's ability to capture environmentally relevant contaminants across all demo sites.

CONCLUSION

A set of **eight high-priority compounds** were consistently detected across all three NBS4AQUAMISSION demo sites (DK, NO, SP) - tilmicosin, tetroxoprim, dipyridamole, protionamide, etofenprox, chlorcyclizine, diclofenac and DEET. While two were already included, the other six high-priority compounds are proposed for inclusion in the WP1 target LC-MS/MS method update (T1.2). These cross-site, high-frequency features represent the most robust chemical indicators for characterizing PP/OMP pollution under SO1 and form the backbone of the prioritization strategy.

ANNEX 1: NBS4AQUAMISSION suspect list

The NBS4AQUAMISSION Suspect Screening List (>500 OMPs/PPs) was compiled by Aarhus University (AU) in 2025 for baseline chemical characterization across the project's demonstration sites (WP1 – Task 1.1). From this extensive list, compounds flagged in the "Target" column are prioritized for future LC-MS/MS quantification under Task 1.3, including wastewater inlets, stormwater-impacted streams, and NbS effluents within WP2.

The suspect screening results reported in this deliverable (D1.1) identified ten high-frequency, cross-site compounds detected across all three NBS4AQUAMISSION demo sites (DK, NO, SP). Among these, two compounds, diclofenac and DEET, are already covered by the existing in-house targeted method. The remaining six compounds, tilmicosin, tetroxoprim, dipyrindamole, protionamide, etofenprox, and chlorcyclizine, are recommended for inclusion in the targeted LC-MS/MS method (T1.2) and are therefore flagged as priorities in the table below. The full dataset for this annex (Annex 1) is deposited in Zenodo and can be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20826069>

Innovation Fund Denmark